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Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted-sulfonamidobenzene azo, 4-sulfophenyl and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)-1(H)-(hetero substituted) pyrazoles and Evaluation of Their Antibacterial Properties

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GREAT importance is being given to pyrazole derivatives due to their uses in therapeutics. Pyrazole compounds with 3- and 5-methyl group are found to possess hypoglycemic activity¹. Isoxazole sulfa-drugs are stable substances and they are characterised by low toxicity and strong activity *in vivo* against bacteria². Substituted-3(2H)pyridazinones are shown to possess antibacterial and anti-fungal activities³.

In continuation of our work in pyrazole series⁴, we wish to report the synthesis of few more compounds, viz. 3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, 4-sulfophenyl and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)-1(H)-(hetero substituted)pyrazole compounds, and screening of their antibacterial properties.

Substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo, benzene azo-4-sulfonic acid and naphthalene azo-4-sulfonic acid derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane (acetylacetone) were prepared by coupling the 2,4-diketopentane with diazotised sulfonamido base, sulfanilic acid and naphthionic acid, respectively (Ia, Ib) in the presence of sodium acetate⁵. The azo derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane obtained was then reacted with four substituted carboxy hydrazides, viz. (i) 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-benzoyl hydrazide)pyrazole, (ii) 3,5-dimethyl-1(H)-(4-nitrophenyl)-4-(methyl carbonyl hydrazide)pyrazole, (iii) 5-phenyl-3-(2-oxymethylene

carbonyl hydrazide)phenyl isoxazole, and (iv) 6-methoxy-2-(4-benzoyl hydrazide)-3(2H)pyridazinone, to furnish the corresponding *N*-substituted-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo)pyrazoles of the type IIa and *N*-substituted-3,5-dimethyl-4-(4-sulfophenyl azo and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)pyrazoles of the type IIb. Hydrazones of the above carboxyhydrazides were also obtained by treating with the azo derivatives of 2,4-diketopentane.

Experimental

The sulfonamides were prepared by standard methods^{6,7}. The azo compounds from 2,4-diketopentane were obtained in 48-75% yield by the method reported earlier⁵. The melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. The elemental analysis of all compounds (C, H, N and S) was found to be satisfactory.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(substituted sulfonamidobenzene azo)pyrazoles: Equimolar quantities of the appropriate carbonyl hydrazide was reacted with 2,4-diketo-3-substituted azo pentane in ethanol under reflux to give the corresponding hydrazones, which were crystallised from aqueous ethanol, and yields ranging from 70-85% (Table 1).

TABLE 1—HYDRAZONES FROM 2,4-DIKETO-3-(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDOBENZENE AZO, 4-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND 4-SULFONAPHTHYL AZO)PENTANE

Sl. no.	X	R	M.p. °C
1	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _a	192
2	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _a	214
3	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	217
4	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _b	178
5	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _b	106
6	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	218
7	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _c	292
8	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _c	126
9	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	208
10	H ₅ C ₂ -	R _d	254
11	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _d	204
12	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	278
13	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _a	310
14	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	104
15	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _b	299
16	4-SO ₂ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	152
17	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _c	330
18	4-SO ₂ H-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	R _d	247

The above hydrazones were converted to the corresponding pyrazoles by refluxing it in glacial acetic acid. The same pyrazoles were also obtained by refluxing 2,4-diketo-3-substituted azo pentane with the respective carbonyl hydrazide in glacial acetic acid for 8-10 h. The separated products were filtered and crystallised from ethanol with yields ranging from 45-75% (Table 2).

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(4-sulfophenyl azo and 4-sulfonaphthyl azo)pyrazoles: 2,4-Diketo-3-(4-sulfophenyl azo) pentane and 2,4-diketo-3-(4-sulfonaphthyl azo) pentane were prepared using the reported proce-

TABLE 2—3,5-DIMETHYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED SULFONAMIDO-BENZENE AZO, 4-SULFOPHENYL AZO AND 4-SULFONAPHTHYL AZO)PYRAZOLE

Sl. no.	X	R	M.p. °C
1	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _a	217
2	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _a	194
3	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	206
4	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _b	103
5	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _b	160
6	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	111
7	HOOCCH ₂ -	R _c	280
8	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _c	166
9	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	222
10	H ₃ C ₂ -	R _d	166
11	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	R _d	211
12	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _a	292
13	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _a	135
14	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _b	267
15	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _b	171
16	4-SO ₃ H-C ₆ H ₄ -	R _c	205
17	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _c	272
18	4-SO ₃ H-C ₁₀ H ₆ -	R _d	286

ture⁵. Azo dicarbonyl compounds were treated with the appropriate carbhydrazides using the procedure mentioned above, to obtain hydrazones (Table 1) and azo pyrazoles (Table 2), respectively.

Screening for antibacterial activity: The compounds in Table 2 have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds were tested by ditch plate technique⁶, using the concentration levels 2 mg and 3 mg per ml.

Compounds 1, 3 and 4 showed complete inhibition of *B. subtilis*. Compounds 12 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *S. aureus*. Compounds 12 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *S. typhi*, whereas compound 18 showed only partial inhibition. Compounds 14 and 16 showed complete inhibition of *P. aeruginosa*. The other compounds showed no activity on the organisms under study. None of the compounds studied showed any activity against *E. coli*. These results were identical for both the concentrations of the compounds studied.

(Ia)

(Ib)

(IIa)

(IIb)

Substituents R = R_a, R_b, R_c, R_d.

(R_d)

X =

(Ia, IIa)

X =

(Ib, IIb)

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Reaction of Nitrosyl Chloride with Steroidal Olefins

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NITROSYL chloride gas was used for chloronitrosation of steroidal alcohols¹ and oximes^{2,3}. The work of Tanabe *et al.*⁴ which dealt with the